

Policy Recommendations for Attracting Investment Capital Contributed to Sustainable Development in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Sustainable development is a goal for many nations, including Vietnam. These measures have helped the Vietnamese economy grow, become more competitive, and industrialise and modernise.

Objective: The study aims to determine the key factors influencing investment capital attraction and sustainable development in Vietnam. The authors also propose policy recommendations to enhance investment capital attraction.

Methodology: The authors conducted a descriptive survey based on the quantitative method and primary data collected directly from managers related to enterprises with investment capital in Vietnam. We collected data from 800 managers from three Vietnamese provinces and ten cities.

Result: Research results show five factors influencing investment capital attraction and sustainable development in Vietnam, each with a five per cent significance. These factors include investment policies, working and living environment, regional connectivity, human resources, and technology. The technological factor exhibits the highest standardised regression coefficient and exerts the most influential effect on attracting investment capital. It plays a crucial role in developing the digital and green economy by facilitating the adoption of clean technology, contributing significantly to sustainable development.

Conclusion: Vietnam's economy, notably investment, has suffered from political and economic instability, diminishing global commerce and investment, epidemics, natural disasters, and climate change.

Unique Contribution: This study has provided empirical data to help understand the factors that could drive sustainable development in Vietnam.

Key Recommendation: Vietnam should establish a comprehensive and stringent legal framework to facilitate the digital transformation and adoption of advanced technology. This component plays a crucial and innovative role in determining the economy's environmentally friendly future.

Keywords: Policy recommendations; investment capital; sustainable development.

Introduction

The necessity for nations to strike a balance between economic development, environmental preservation, and social equality has led to the rise of sustainable development as a top international priority in recent years. Managing its economic trajectory while addressing social injustice, climate change, and environmental degradation is a huge challenge for Vietnam's quickly rising economy. To achieve sustainable development, large sums of investment must be mobilised to fund projects and initiatives that will positively impact society and the environment in the long run.

At present, attracting investment capital alongside mitigating environmental degradation is an essential investment trend; concurrently, the nations receiving investment are increasingly

focused on enhancing environmental protection legislation. Therefore, when a country gets clean, green capital investment projects, it will have the opportunity to receive modern, environmentally friendly treatment technologies, both increasing economic benefits and ensuring the environment (Mehmood et al., 2021; Bailey, 2018). Investment capital enhances the environment by facilitating the introduction of energy-efficient products, diminishing reliance on conventional raw materials or energy sources, and providing solutions to optimise production efficiency and promote effective environmental protection practices (Abdouli & Hammami, 2020). Furthermore, international corporations exert a spillover effect on domestic enterprises by disseminating modern technology, professional expertise, and the necessity to adhere to stringent environmental norms.

Besides, the interest of international investors in the green economy and production has had favourable spillover effects on the Vietnamese economy. The ecological industrial park (IP) model has garnered significant attention due to enhanced policies and heightened investment from industrial real estate development firms. Eco-IP refers to IPs designated as eco-IPs within the context of the project executing Eco-IPs in Vietnam, adhering to the methodology of the Global Eco-IP Program. On the other hand, the IP Management Board also has a more positive view of environmental protection as a prerequisite for attracting investment capital (Mitra & Abedin, 2021). Previously, environmental protection was often viewed as increasing costs, thus inconsistent with economic benefits. However, IPs are now paying more attention to screening and assessing environmental impacts to ensure that investment projects will be environmentally friendly.

Moreover, investment capital inflows into Vietnam have shown favourable developments in both volume and calibre. Investment projects are progressively aligning with Vietnam's green and sustainable development objectives. Therefore, this study aims to determine the critical factors influencing investment capital attraction and sustainable development and provide policy recommendations for managers and the Government to foster investment capital attraction and sustainable development in Vietnam.

Literature Review

Sustainable Development (SUS)

Sustainability refers to the equilibrium and preservation of activities at a level that can be sustained indefinitely without detrimental effects on the natural environment, resource depletion, or adverse repercussions for future generations. Sustainability encompasses three primary pillars: economic, social, and environmental, referred to as the 3Ps: Profit, People, and Planet (Etim et al., 2019). Furthermore, economic sustainability pertains to preserving economic growth and development without exhausting the economy's resources. Social sustainability emphasises ensuring social justice equality and improving the quality of life for all, including protecting the rights and well-being of communities and individuals. Environmental sustainability focuses on preserving the natural environment to ensure that natural resources are not depleted and that ecosystems can continue to support life (Avrampou et al., 2019). Achieving sustainable development requires a comprehensive and integrated approach that considers the linkages between economic, social, and environmental pillars.

Investment Capital Attraction (CAP)

Attracting investment capital involves the strategic utilisation and mobilisation of financial resources to fulfil the capital requirements for economic development. Attracting investment capital necessitates a synthesis of mechanisms and policies, encompassing the legal framework and technical infrastructure, as well as societal, resource, and environmental factors, to entice investors' capital in science and technology for production and business to attain specific objectives (Adam et al., 2020). Investment capital attraction refers to the aggregate expenditure

incurred by an investor to engage in investment activities derived from two principal sources: domestic capital and foreign capital. Investment capital fosters comprehensive economic growth and quality enhancement (Kumari & Sharma, 2018).

Investment Policies (POL)

Investment policies include governmental rules regarding taxation, investment incentives, administrative protocols, and legal frameworks pertinent to corporate operations. These policies directly influence domestic and international investors' capacity to attract capital (Bailey, 2018). One of the attractiveness of the investment environment can be expressed through tax incentives—especially corporate income tax for a certain period by industry, field, and location. Taxes directly impact the enterprise's income. High tax rates will cause subjects to balance implementing institutions correctly or wriggle through, reducing the investment environment's attractiveness and economic growth (Hsu et al., 2019).

Working and Living Environment (ENV)

This factor includes the quality of life, infrastructure, healthcare, education, and environmental aspects such as air and water quality. It is crucial in attracting skilled professionals, managers, and high-calibre investors (Kurul & Yalta, 2017). The studies analysed the living and working environment reflected through cultural, educational, and medical factors. The author views the environment as a condition, basis, and prerequisite for sustainable socio-economic development, emphasising the need to prioritise environmental integrity over economic expansion (Olson & Morton, 2018).

Regional Connectivity (CON)

Regional connectivity refers to the transportation, logistics, trade, and communication linkages between different areas within a country or between countries. This includes road networks, airways, seaports, and digital communication infrastructure (Sokang, 2018). The studies showed that regional and intra-regional links are increasingly focused and achieve significant results. The issue of decentralisation is becoming more straightforward and more transparent. Organisations and inter-regional cooperation mechanisms are gradually being formed. Production forces and adjusted development planning have been reallocated to suit the strengths of each locality, especially inter-provincial and international road traffic infrastructure (Xie & Lin, 2022).

Human Resources (HUM)

This factor pertains to the quality and availability of the workforce, including education levels, professional skills, and adaptability to technological advancements. Human resources are critical to sustainable development and creating a competitive edge (Wu & He, 2018). The studies showed that labour quality manifests through educational, professional skills, health, and discipline. Thus, human resources are the central resource that determines socio-economic growth and development. It is the decisive factor in exploiting, using, protecting, and regenerating other resources (Taguchi & Khinsamone, 2018). Human capital, also known as human capital, is the source of habits, knowledge, social attributes, and personality expressed in the ability to perform labour to create economic value.

Technology (TEC)

Technology includes IT infrastructure, research and development (R&D) capabilities, technology adoption in production and services, and access to advanced technologies. Investment in science and technology has not been focused, especially in scientific projects with conditions for research and application, linking with the national economic sectors (Sirag

et al., 2018). The studies showed that capacity building for endogenous technology still has many shortcomings. This factor prevents science and technology from being connected to the needs and activities of the socio-economic sectors. The results of the research have been slowly put into practical application (Nurlanova et al., 2018; Nantharath & Kang, 2019). The technology level is much lower than in other countries; the creation of new technologies is limited, failing to meet its socio-economic development.

Theoretical Framework

Investment Policies (POL) Affecting Investment Capital Attraction (CAP) and Sustainable Development (SUS)

Favourable investment policies, such as tax incentives for strategic industries or simplified administrative procedures, make it easier for investors to engage and commit capital. Conversely, restrictive policies can create barriers, reducing the attractiveness to investors (Fan et al., 2018). In order to gain investors' trust, the government must keep its policies stable and open. Favourable conditions, such as property leasing, tax system transparency, and simplified legal processes, are essential investment drivers, as demonstrated by the investment policies. It is critical to have bold and creative leadership at the regional level (Elheddad, 2018; Thuy & Tam, 2023). Local and foreign investors place a premium on ease of doing business and a focus on transparency and efficiency. Therefore, H1 and H2 are proposed in Figure 1.

Working and Living Environment (ENV) Affecting Investment Capital Attraction (CAP) and Sustainable Development (SUS)

Countries or regions with better living standards, lower pollution levels, more developed infrastructure, and better public services tend to attract investments in the long run. On the flip side, strategic investors who prioritise sustainable development see environmental concerns and poor infrastructure as major deterrents to investment (Kurul & Yalta, 2017). An important factor in investment decisions is the quality of the working and living environment, which encompasses the government's ability to resolve conflicts, the strength of the education system, and the availability of top-notch healthcare (Olson & Morton, 2018; Thuy & Tam, 2023). Businesses can rest assured that their human resource demands will be met because the educational system is in sync with the industry's. Therefore, H3 and H4 are proposed in Figure 1.

Regional Connectivity (CON) Affecting Investment Capital Attraction (CAP) and Sustainable Development (SUS)

Businesses and investors can use excellent regional connections to transport goods efficiently, opening up new consumer markets and expanding their operations (Xie & Lin, 2022; Thuy & Tam, 2023). Several factors significantly impact investment choices, including strong supply chains, inter-provincial collaboration, and the prevalence of supporting industries across the nation. Productivity rises due to improved logistics and cost-effective manufacturing made possible by regional solid connectivity (Sokang, 2018). The coordinated economic activities across the country's provinces demonstrate Vietnam's ability to function as a single economic zone, opening up business growth opportunities. Thus, H5 and H6 are proposed in Figure 1.

Human Resources (HUM) Affecting Investment Capital Attraction (CAP) and Sustainable Development (SUS)

To meet the demands of modern industries, a young and abundant workforce must invest significantly in education and skill development. National competitiveness, worker productivity, and workforce quality can all be enhanced by investments in education and training (Wu & He, 2018). Investors place a premium on a skilled labour force that is easily

accessible through vocational training institutes and has access to managerial recruitment opportunities. One advantage highlighted is the workforce, known for its low level of competence. There are many leeways for companies to grow thanks to the availability of cheap labour and flexible, skilled workers (Taguchi & Khinsamone, 2018; Thuy & Tam, 2023). Human capital development through training programs ensures a competitive workforce that is able to embrace new technology and success for companies. Thus, H7 & H8 proposed in Figure 1.

Technology (TEC) Affecting Investment Capital Attraction (CAP) and Sustainable Development (SUS)

Massive efforts are being made to foster high-tech industries and accelerate digital transformation. There will be greater investment opportunities and longer-term economic growth if we embrace new technologies and increase our research and development capacities (Sirag et al., 2018). In order to maximise profits and compete on a global scale, investors will probably look for areas that have strong technological skills. Timely training for technology transfer, support for chosen industries, and intellectual property protection are some of Vietnam's most attractive features to investors (Nurlanova et al., 2018; Nantharath & Kang, 2019). Improve operational efficiency and competitiveness by prioritising technical development, operating securely, and leveraging innovative technology. Therefore, hypotheses H9 and H10 are proposed in Figure 1.

Investment Capital Attraction (CAP) Affecting Sustainable Development (SUS)

The global trend has many fluctuations and crises. Along with that are increasingly strict requirements of the supply chain, higher standards of the market, and social responsibility of enterprises towards the environment, governance, and society (Abdouli & Hammami, 2020; Thuy & Tam, 2023). Sustainable development requirement creates challenges, requiring businesses to invest in production and responsibly attract investment capital from domestic and foreign investors, use high technology, modern technology, clean, environmentally friendly technology, and create products with high added value for sustainable development (Mitra & Abedin, 2021). In addition, proactively inviting and working with investors, strengthening administrative reform, and attracting many essential investment projects, promoting sustainable development. Therefore, hypothesis H11 is proposed in Figure 1.

After examining the studies above, the authors developed a research model of five components that impact investment capital attraction and sustainable development in Figure 1.

Source: The authors suggested

Figure 1: The framework for five factors affecting the investment capital attraction and sustainable development

Figure 1 illustrates five factors affecting Vietnam's investment capital attraction and sustainable development.

Research Methods

The authors included two primary quantitative steps in the study's design. These stages are necessary for investigating, evaluating, and analyzing the relationship between variables in a theoretical model and detailed contents, and they are followed by a total of twelve steps.

In the first step, the writers present the objectives that are intended to be examined, evaluated, and analyzed from the perspective of the theoretical model. In light of the findings, prepare a proposal for a research report. The scales created from earlier research should be fine-tuned and improved to suit the Vietnamese context, considering the cultural, linguistic, and developmental distinctions.

During the second step of the research process, the authors conducted in-depth interviews using the quantitative research approach based on convenience sampling. Fifteen managers from the investment capital attraction and sustainable development departments and fifteen experienced investors participated in the event. All of the interviews were carried out virtually through direct telephone calls.

At this point, the authors had reached a point when the number of interviews had reached saturation, and no fresh aspects were emerging. Extensive interviews provided evidence that the study scales used in the model are applicable.

The writers conducted quantitative research in the fourth step of the preliminary and formal phases. For data collection, the research team used convenience sampling, with the sample size chosen based on different characteristics.

In the fifth step, the sample size is established by taking into account some different processing methods, including Cronbach's alpha (with a threshold of more than 0.7), Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The evaluation of the model's fit is conducted by utilising the following criteria: the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) must be greater than or equal to 0.900, the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) must be greater than or equal to 0.900, the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) must be greater than or equal to 0.900, and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) must be less than or equal to 0.1.

In the sixth step, we use empirical approaches specific to each analytical strategy to determine the sample size. We can find the minimum sample size ($n = 5 * m$) by multiplying the total number of observed variables by five. The minimum sample size for exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is 125, whereas the minimum for multiple regression analysis is 98, based on a study involving 27 observed variables. The study utilised 800 survey samples from three different provinces and one city in Vietnam. These provinces and cities were Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai Province, Binh Duong Province, and Ba Ria-Vung Tau Province, among others. The population under research is comprised of managers, and there are around 10,000 managers situated throughout Vietnam.

In the seventh step, the authors implemented the questionnaire using a Likert scale with five levels: one indicates severe disagreement, and five indicates strong agreement. In total, 800 questionnaires for the survey were handed out, and 785 replies that were considered legitimate were gathered. Data analysis was carried out with the assistance of the SPSS software, and convenience sampling was utilised (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 8: The survey was carried out in three different provinces of Vietnam and in the city of 01 between July and December 2023. Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam's largest city and economic hub city, had two hundred managers. (2) Dong Nai included two hundred managers: Dong Nai, located close to Ho Chi Minh City, provides insights into an industrially developed and suburban atmosphere. (3) As another province quickly industrialised, Binh Duong had two hundred managers. Ba Ria-Vung Tau had a total of two hundred managers. This coastal region, which is well-known for its tourist and oil sectors, brings a fresh point of view to the investigation (Hair et al., 2018).

The ninth step was for the writers to get feedback from 785 managers using a thorough quantitative survey. The authors used Cronbach's Alpha to check the scales' reliability and internal consistency, ensuring the data is legitimate and trustworthy. It was determined that the Cronbach's alpha coefficients were more than 0.7. A pilot test was done before the actual survey to build the questionnaire and make sure the questions were relevant and clear. The official study used confirmatory factor analysis (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 10: The writers used the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method to test the model's efficacy and research assumptions. Early scale evaluations were made using SPSS 20.0 and Amos. The use of EFA and CFA analyses, in conjunction with assessing model fit and study assumptions, allowed this to be accomplished. The author used descriptive statistics to concisely summarise the demographic data and overall trends. The authors employed SEM to assess the assumptions established in the theoretical model. This enabled them to ascertain the magnitude and orientation of the correlations among the variables.

In the eleventh step, the authors conducted research to validate and standardise the scales and questionnaires. The authors' use of a systematic approach guarantees that the presentation of the study process, aims, methodology, findings, and analysis is clear and complete.

Step 12: The authors expressed their conclusions and suggested policy changes to improve Vietnam's ability to attract investment capital and foster sustainable development.

Study Results

From 2019 to now, investment in sustainable development has been estimated at more than many billion USD in Vietnam, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, and this investment source has not been interrupted. The research findings show that five factors affect investment capital attraction and that investment capital attraction affects sustainable development, as shown in the results below.

Table 1: Testing Cronbach's alpha, mean, and standard deviation value for five factors

Code Items	Number of items	Code	Cronbach's alpha	Mean	Std. Deviation
Investment policies (POL)	4	POL1, POL2, POL3, POL4	0.866	2.394	0.571
Working and living environment (ENV)	4	ENV1, ENV2, ENV3, ENV4	0.956	3.062	0.930
Regional connectivity (CON)	4	CON1, CON2, CON3, CON4	0.856	3.390	0.774
Human resources (HUM)	4	HUM1, HUM2, HUM3, HUM4	0.943	3.053	0.905
Technology (TEC)	4	TEC1, TEC2, TEC3, TEC4	0.956	3.087	0.927
Investment capital attraction (CAP)	3	CAP1, CAP2, CAP3	0.940	3.343	0.913
Sustainable development (SUS)	4	SUS1, SUS2, SUS3, SUS4	0.869	2.382	0.570

Source: calculations by the authors

Table 1 delineates the outcomes of Cronbach's alpha assessment alongside the mean and standard deviation metrics for the five principal factors mentioned above, in addition to two outcome variables: Investment capital attraction and sustainable development. The items' internal consistency within each factor is evaluated by Cronbach's alpha values. For reliability, a Cronbach's alpha value above 0.7 is considered acceptable, a number over 0.8 indicates high reliability and a value over 0.9 indicates extraordinary reliability.

Source: The results from SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Figure 2: The five elements affect the attractiveness of investment capital and sustainable development in Vietnam

The five main factors influencing the attractiveness of investment capital and sustainable development were examined using the model fit indices at a significance level of 0.05. The study's results highlight the intricate relationships between sustainable development, human resources, regional connectivity, policy, and technology that affect investment climate to attract investment and promote long-term growth that benefits society and the economy.

Table 2: Testing five factors influencing the investment capital attraction and sustainable development

Relationships	Standardized estimate	Unstandardized estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Result
CAP <--- POL	0.164	0.086	0.059	2.794	0.005	Accepted H1
CAP <--- ENV	0.076	0.087	0.027	2.776	0.006	Accepted H3
CAP <--- CON	0.172	0.168	0.034	5.090	***	Accepted H5
CAP <--- HUM	0.084	0.104	0.026	3.293	***	Accepted H7
CAP <--- TEC	0.481	0.540	0.030	16.300	***	Accepted H9
SUS <--- CAP	0.179	0.332	0.023	7.951	***	Accepted H11
SUS <--- POL	0.149	0.145	0.033	4.503	***	Accepted H2
SUS <--- ENV	0.074	0.157	0.016	4.761	***	Accepted H4
SUS <--- CON	0.069	0.125	0.019	3.705	***	Accepted H6
SUS <--- HUM	0.028	0.065	0.013	2.238	0.025	Accepted H8
SUS <--- TEC	0.141	0.292	0.019	7.335	***	Accepted H10

The data was analyzed using SPSS 20.0, Amos, and the significance level is ***, equal to 0.01.

Table 2 reflects the hypothesis testing results on the relationships between the five factors and their impact on investment capital attraction and sustainable development. The results show both standardised and unstandardised estimates, standard errors, critical ratios, p-values, and whether the hypotheses were accepted with statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 3: Testing average variance extracted for the investment capital attraction and sustainable development

Code	CR	AVE	MSV	Results
CON	0.852	0.600	0.027	Very good
TEC	0.957	0.847	0.312	Very good
ENV	0.956	0.845	0.042	Very good
HUM	0.943	0.806	0.020	Very good
SUS	0.870	0.630	0.301	Very good
POL	0.867	0.623	0.024	Very good
CAP	0.941	0.843	0.312	Very good

The data was analyzed using SPSS 20.0, Amos.

Table 3 shows that composite reliability measures the internal consistency of the items representing each factor, similar to Cronbach's alpha. CR values above 0.7 are generally considered acceptable, and values above 0.9 indicate excellent reliability. The CR, AVE, and MSV testing results across the seven constructs suggest that the measurement model has excellent internal consistency convergent and discriminant validity. These findings indicate that the constructs used in your investment capital attraction and sustainable development analysis are reliable and valid.

Table 4: Testing Bootstrap based on 20.000 samples for the investment capital attraction and sustainable development

Parameter	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias	CR	Results
CAP <--- POL	0.081	0.002	0.147	0.005	0.003	1.67	Good
CAP <--- ENV	0.028	0.001	0.074	0.002	0.002	1.00	Good
CAP <--- CON	0.042	0.001	0.166	0.003	0.003	1.00	Good
CAP <--- HUM	0.029	0.001	0.075	0.004	0.003	1.33	Good
CAP <--- TEC	0.041	0.001	0.481	0.000	0.001	0.00	Good
SUS <--- CAP	0.025	0.001	0.183	0.001	0.001	1.00	Good
SUS <--- POL	0.054	0.001	0.132	0.001	0.002	0.50	Good
SUS <--- ENV	0.017	0.000	0.068	0.003	0.002	1.50	Good
SUS <--- CON	0.021	0.000	0.063	0.001	0.001	6.00	Good
SUS <--- HUM	0.021	0.000	0.032	0.003	0.002	1.50	Good
SUS <--- TEC	0.021	0.000	0.138	0.002	0.003	0.67	Good

The authors used SPSS 20.0, Amos, as a data source.

Table 4 presents the estimate's Critical Ratio (CR) ratio to its standard error. A higher CR value (typically > 1.96) would indicate statistical significance at the 95% confidence level. However, the CR values in the range of 1.00 - 6.00 reported in this table generally indicate good results

based on this sample size and bootstrap replication. The bootstrap results suggest that the relationships between the factors of investment capital attraction are the most influential factors, which include technology for investment capital attraction and regional connectivity for sustainable development.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from this analysis highlight the critical factors influencing investment capital attraction and sustainable development in Vietnam. The study employs structural equation modelling and bootstrap analysis to furnish compelling evidence regarding the influence of factors such as investment policies, working and living conditions, regional connectivity, human resources, and technology on investment dynamics and sustainable development. Based on the high standardised estimate of 0.481 and little bias in the SEM and bootstrap tests, the study concludes that technology substantially impacts the allure of investment capital. Given technology's enormous influence, Vietnam places an ever-increasing premium on digital transformation, R&D, and IP protection. The nation's support for technological advancement is an important factor in attracting investors, making technology an important factor in investment decisions. The statistics also corroborated attracting investment capital and achieving sustainable development. Capital attraction promotes long-term economic growth by creating jobs, improving living standards, and funding conservation efforts. Vietnamese sustainable development goals rely heavily on investment attraction, as shown by the positive standardised estimate of 0.179. The findings show these elements' relative strength and importance, providing policymakers and stakeholders with practical information.

(1) The largest factor on investment capital attraction is technology (TEC), with a normalised estimate of 0.481 ($p < 0.001$). Technological infrastructure and innovation are crucial to attracting investment capital. Technology-driven regions attract investors because they boost efficiency and competitiveness. The positive correlation between TEC and sustainable development (0.141, $p < 0.001$) indicates that investing in technology draws capital and promotes sustainability. Thus, Vietnam should prioritise technical advances in clean energy, digitalisation, and sustainable production to increase economic and sustainability outcomes.

(2) Regional connectedness (CON) significantly impacts investment capital attraction (0.172, $p < 0.001$) and marginally impacts sustainable development (0.069, $p < 0.001$). Well-developed transportation, communication, and logistics networks facilitate investment inflows. While technology has a greater impact on sustainable development, enhanced connectivity aids sustainable economic operations. Green infrastructure projects like eco-friendly transportation systems can boost regional connectivity's sustainable development benefits.

(3) Investment policies (POL) positively correlate with investment capital attraction (0.164, $p = 0.005$) and sustainable development (0.149, $p < 0.001$). This emphasises the necessity of good regulatory and policy environments for investment. Clear, consistent, and transparent regulations that stimulate green investments, expedite administrative processes, and incentivise sustainable projects might attract more investors to Vietnam's sustainable development goals. The strong impact of POL on sustainable development implies that policy reforms can directly affect sustainability by directing money to environmentally and socially responsible sectors.

(4) Human resources (HUM) significantly correlate with investment capital attractiveness (0.084, $p < 0.001$) but have a lesser impact on sustainable development (0.028, $p = 0.025$). This suggests that skilled labor attracts investment but contributes little to sustainable development. Workforce skills may need to be aligned with sustainable industry needs. Human resource training in sustainability-related disciplines like green technologies and environmental management can boost investment attraction and sustainability outcomes.

(5) Low but significant impact of working and living environment (ENV) on investment capital attraction (0.076, $p = 0.006$) and sustainable development (0.074, $p < 0.001$). The influence is smaller than other characteristics, but the data show that a good work-life balance attracts investment. Investors may want safe, high-quality, and ecologically friendly areas. Vietnam can attract sustainable investments by improving environmental standards and living circumstances.

(6) The relationship between investment capital attraction (CAP) and sustainable development (SUS) is significant (0.179, $p < 0.001$), indicating that attracting investment capital is crucial for sustainable development. Through the characteristics outlined, Vietnam can attract more funds to participate in sustainability programs that enhance long-term environmental and social development.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Improving key policy domains is crucial if Vietnam is to attract investment capital for sustainable development. Investing in cutting-edge technology, strengthening regional ties, creating a skilled and adaptable workforce, and simplifying administrative processes are all ways the country might increase its economy. Vietnam is a captivating investment destination that supports global sustainability values, and these beliefs align with the larger goals of socioeconomic development and environmental protection. This academic approach provides a comprehensive strategy for addressing the key factors influencing investment capital attraction, ensuring that policies foster economic growth and long-term sustainability in line with global SDGs. Based on the findings, the authors made proposals to simultaneously improve the investment capital attraction and sustainable development in Vietnam following:

1. Investment policies affecting investment capital attraction based on the standardised estimate of 0.164 and p-value of 0.005. The result indicated that investment policies have a statistically significant and positive influence on capital attraction. The results indicated that advantageous policies, particularly in premises leasing, tax system transparency, and efficient legal procedures, are critical motivators for investment in Vietnam. The proactive and innovative leadership at the local level also plays a pivotal role. Favourable investment policies foster an attractive business environment, enhancing Vietnam's competitiveness in the global investment arena. Focusing on transparency and efficiency reduces bureaucratic hurdles, thereby improving ease of business, which is crucial for local and foreign investors.

2. The working and living environment affects investment capital attraction, based on the standardised estimate of 0.076 with a p-value of 0.006. This shows that the working and living environment positively impacts investment capital attraction. Therefore, enterprises should build a working and living environment encompassing governmental efficiency in dispute resolution, a developed education system, and access to high-quality healthcare, which are significant factors in investment decisions. By ensuring a pristine living environment and a reasonable cost of living, Vietnam appeals not only to investors but also to a skilled workforce, which is essential for the operational success of businesses. The education system's alignment with enterprise needs ensures that human resources are tailored to the demands of the business sector.

3. Regional connectivity affects investment capital attraction based on the standardized estimate of 0.172 and a highly significant p-value is 0.001, and regional connectivity strongly influences investment capital attraction. Thus, Vietnam should have policies for supporting industries across the country, coupled with inter-provincial cooperation and robust supply chains, which greatly influence investment decisions. Strong regional connectivity facilitates cost-efficient production and streamlined logistics, contributing to higher productivity. The well-coordinated economic activities between provinces demonstrate Vietnam's ability to function as a cohesive economic region, making it easier for businesses to expand their

operations.

4. The standardised estimate for the effect of human resources on investment capital attraction is 0.084, and the corresponding p-value is 0.001. Human resources significantly impact investment capital attraction. To keep its human capital competitive advantage, Vietnam should keep investing in education, especially vocational training. An important factor for investors to consider is the availability of a trained workforce, mainly through vocational training institutes, and the ease of recruiting managers. This consideration should inform training programs. The low-skilled workforce in Vietnam is also emphasized as a strength. Companies may increase operations with ease when they have access to cheap labor and competent people who are highly adaptable. Vietnam's training programs for human capital development keep workers competitive and open to new technology, which helps businesses expand over time.

5. With a p-value of 0.001 and a normalized estimate of 0.084, we can measure the effect of technology on the allure of investment capital. An important factor in luring investment money is the human resources element. The Vietnamese government should keep investing in research and development of new technologies, particularly in areas that promote creativity and environmental responsibility. To encourage long-term growth and attract top-tier investment, it is necessary to provide incentives for R&D while simultaneously strengthening intellectual property protection. Quick training for technology transfer, support for preferred industries, and protection of intellectual property are some of Vietnam's selling points to investors. Vietnam is committed to building an innovative economy, as seen by its emphasis on research funding and technology transfer. Businesses are able to run safely and make use of innovative technology to boost efficiency and competitiveness because the government supports and protects intellectual property rights.

Limitations and future research: Access to comprehensive data on investment patterns is limited, which could make it challenging to examine Vietnam's investment capital attractiveness, especially in emerging sectors like sustainable industries and technology. Because of this limitation, the study's comprehensiveness and the ability to draw reliable conclusions may suffer. The allure of investment capital in Vietnam is influenced by sector-specific dynamics, which should be investigated in future studies. It is possible to gain valuable insights for sector-specific policy recommendations by studying the challenges and opportunities faced by key industries, such as renewable energy, IT, and manufacturing.

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